

DATA BY COMBINING MAIL THROUGH TO SEND METHODS

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INTRODUCTION

Raising the morale of young people and discovering highly qualified specialists among them is at the center of the strong social policy conducted for the youth, for the future and benefit of the youth in our republic.

In the world experience, one of the important goals of higher education is the professional development of students, the formation of their cognitive skills and the practical application of the acquired knowledge, skills, skills and competencies to life. Uzbekistan Republic ministers in the decree of the court No. PF-5953 of March 2, 2020 "2020/2021 academic year from the year starting from republic higher education in institutions study process step by step credit module to the system transfer order current it is said . In this system of students independent to work separated hours share increased _

That's it basically higher education in institutions education system quality increase in order to traditional teaching tools with one in line modern information and communication technologies Create and apply need will be This issue solution to do for to teach intended software tools , including electron educational and methodological complexes work exit need will be Usually computer constant technical tool as place holds _ Thus the student from computer _ placed issue appropriate and fast point in reaching information from technologies appropriate use the basics absorbs .

Data by combining mail through to send methods

Documents or information by combining mail through to send for the following common order done increase can :

Data preparation : Documents from sending before , them complete and right in the format preparation necessary _ Data clear , simple and come came out in the form will be edited .

Electronic mail notification preparation : Data from combining then , this information electron mail notification through to send for new electron letter is made . In the letter this of documents content and this documents acceptance by , or him how to use need about short definition to be it is necessary

Mail source select : Documents to send for mail source is selected . If your your goal documents by combining to send if so , yours service from your guides used without all necessary documents to send for data warehouses choose can _

Notice for information input : Mail of the letter content in the department documents combined about short comment and information organize reach need _ This is an explanation short and understood to be it is necessary

Source information input : Notice content in the section , documents combined source information (e- mail source or using another source) is added . This is the source information , documents acceptance by doing get for valid will be

The letter send : The letter prepared and source information with from being filled then , her targeted source mail through is sent . Remember transition service _ _ pointers the letter how acceptance to do and him study explained to be need. This process basically electron mail letters to send for done is increased . If the documents combine and in sending another formats want to use if so , that's it work perform for documents electron to files change need will be and them one electron file in the form of attach and later to send can _

Data storage : It stores data _ long term storage and his to information interest , approx word do , and addition services done increase for necessary has been environment provide in order to works _

Data management : These systems information manage and they are between search , sort , edit and another management own into takes _

Data distribution : Warehouses , information users or another systems with in exchange average has been departments as service does _ This is the data another to applications transfer or to them access for road opens.data warehouses , usually service _ doing to the branch and information storage for desired in the format has been different data types uses _ This warehouses , sites , mobile applications , computer programs and another from platforms use through users with in touch will be The same while , they common data from bases , personal from data , company from information , from information and another kind of from the data use for work developed to be can _

Information warehouse it 's sorted information keeper and again working information model is considered Simpler by doing in other words one different kind of information in itself keeper and given requests through them present doer model _ An example for , books shelf , this data warehouse is , that is one different type (books) objects in itself saves , or if not telephone numbers written booklet , this on the ground name , phone number such as one different type data is stored

Medicine in the field each one the patient for separated medical card too information _ _ warehouse is considered Information warehouse manage system is this data storage nest harvest hooker _ _ information again working and seeker system is considered Short by doing in other words , MOBT all processes done increases . Information warehouse only information keeps the rest all things Information _ _ idiom manage system (MOBT) performs .

of MBBT main features _ _ only information input and in storage used procedures composition without their _ structure too describes . Data in itself save and under MBBT managed file before data bank , later and « Data base _ _ managed started _ Data manage system .

Q 's house to properties has :

- files collection makes sense agreement powers up ;
- data on the work conduct language with provides ;
- each different from stops after information again restores ;
- one how many of users parallel work provides

MB one or one how many to the models based on to be can _ Har how to the model his own with properties (parameters). descriptive object as to look can _ That's it object on something if he does the action will be of MB models three main types Available :

Relational , hierarchical and semantic network .

Relational (lat in the language relatio-relationship from the word obtained) in the model information storage him organize doer parts between to relationships based on the most simple there are two of them measured massive or from the table consists of will be Complicated information models mother so of tables mutually connected from the collection consists of

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